

Towards a regulatory spray drift model for risk assessment purposes

Andrew C. Chapple

with: Ed Casanova, Naresh Pai, and
Zhenglei Gao

Bayer AG, Crop Science Division,
Monheim, DE

Agenda

- // Drift models
- // Why do we need a drift model?
 - // Tiered RA for drift
 - // The
- // The Casanova Drift Model
- // Future research and development needs to support drift modelling

The “available” spray or vapour drift models (EU)

Three types of active substance drift: spray, dust, and vapour.

Two general approaches to modelling: mechanistic v. [data driven].

// For arable crops:

// SiMod from Silsoe Spray Application Unit (UK). Sophisticated inputs.

// IDEFICS from WUR-PRI (NL). Something of a “black box”

// Casanova (in development but useable): simpler than the above two.

// Belgian CFD model (but collecting dust). Very difficult to set up and run.

// [Various database driven models (Rautmann, AgDrift, SETAC DRAW Bayesian regression model)]

// For orchards (and vines):

// Belgian CFD model

// [Dutch orchard model (but database driven)]

// For vapour:

// Various plume dispersion models (e.g., ADMS)

An overview of EU-available models...

(Not complete)

Note: no mention of spray drift models...

Colour coding:

Why do we need drift models?

- // To date, the Rautmann drift tables have been sufficient, but these are under scrutiny (and are rather old!)
- // Drift RA is a single Tier; higher tier approaches to an RA involving drift build on the drift tables (and there are no other options)
- // In a properly structured tiered RA, a regulatory model is one of the key component:
 - // C.f.: ground water, surface water. The tier involves various stages, ether experimental (e.g., ecotox studies) to interpolations within data sets (e.g., birds and small mammals RUDs) to various modelling approaches (previous slide) to full scale field trials.
- // Arable crop drift values are in the process of being reassessed by EFSA – now ongoing – and are likely to be 3x to 15x higher than the current drift tables.
- // For non-target arthropods (NTAs) and non-target terrestrial pants (NTTPs), increased drift values are about a third of the overall increase in difficulty of regulatory acceptance. This brings the near-off-crop to prominence as an environmental compartment.
 - // Historically, water has been the principal environmental issue but the very limited mitigation options available for NTAs/NTTPs means that the near-off-crop will be of equivalent importance.

A Tiered RA for drift

A tiered RA for drift was the principal objective of SETAC DRAW. The Workshops and a lot subsequent work outside DRAW have delivered:

- 1. Data:** SETAC DRAW database (approx. 2200 drift trial) is now hosted at INRAE and is currently open to the researchers who supplied the data (8 EU countries plus Canada).
- 2. Statistical tools:** A Bayesian regression model based on the database can be used to explore scenarios as well as the confidence intervals around the drift curves generated.
- 3. Relevant scenarios:** The weakest link in the chain. Currently available data is very limited, mainly focused on N. Europe (esp. UK).
- 4. A model:** two models already exist. Neither are truly in the public domain, nor is the code available for outside development or scrutiny.
- 5. Up-to-date methodologies for drift trials:** the SETAC DRAW arable crop drift protocol is a template for future drift trials.
- 6. Laboratory methods:** Link actual spray drift to tiered testing (more on this at AAB IAPA, 2022, Sept. 2022 Munster, DE).
- 7. Trial designs:** NOED (no observable effect distance) trials – published and used by Syngenta and Bayer. These are the top tier assessments.

The Casanova Drift Model

Developed in-house by Ed Casanova (ex-Monsanto, now in Bayer's Enabling Technology Team) as a tool for screening formulations to limit field trials.

Original programming in MathCad (so not user-friendly). Converted to 'R' and C++.

Calibrated and validated against the Spray Drift Task Force arable data sets and then against internal field trial data.

Principal components of model:

- // Droplet size distribution (DSD) – temporal data and at operating pressure to be modelled
- // Nozzle flow vs. pressure (velocity of droplet obtained here)
- // Tank solution density, total dissolved solids (DS) concentration, and check between intended application rate (IAR) for active, DS, NF, and Tractor speed (TS) (also important for evaporation).
- // Determination of wet bulb T depression (DTwb) for use in droplet evaporation equation
- // Wind velocity profile with elevation and horizontal variability in wind direction around mean relative to sprayed field – turbulence in direction of wind only. (Remaining two dimensions to be added.)
- // Deposition of droplets – converted to a deposition curve.

The Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

SiMod, IDEFICS, and Casanova all follow the same physical descriptions. CDM is simpler than SiMod. [E.g., it does not include a droplet detrainment component nor any approach to crop canopies. (This is a level of sophistication that may come with time.)] CDM differs from SiMod in taking a different approach to droplet sampling. Along with optimized routines, this makes it much faster.

CDM needs improvement / development on:

- // Turbulence description
- // Vertical distribution of droplets in flight
- // Flexibility in setting up the spray boom (currently a single 27 m boom is modelled)
- // Crop interception / filtration. (Currently limited to bare ground / short grass)

However, unlike the other arable crop drift models:

- // It is in the public domain already.
- // It comes with a nozzle drop spectra library (all EU standard nozzles and pressures as found in the SETAC DRAW database)
- // All code (R and C++) will be freely available.

Digression to the model

A demonstration of just one run.

- // Average French trial set conditions
- // xxx nozzle at xxx kPa
- // xxx ind speed, xxx %RH and xxx T°

Calibration and Validation

To be published at AAB International Advances in Spray Application, Munster, Sept. 2022

[Suffice to say, it works...]

Calibration and Validation

What is more interesting and more relevant to the future of arable crop drift modelling is what has been learnt along the way, during SETAC DRAW and in the development of this model.

Some insights so far.

- // Any model has to be:
 - // useable in any regulatory domain (EU, USA, LATAM) or country.
 - // deal with differences in upwind structures that affect the overall wind profile.
 - // tuneable to a given country's drift trials and data.
 - // agnostic with respect to inputs such as drop spectra and variability from sources such as sampler capture efficiency.
 - // able to generate not just deposition curves but also short range aerial drift (linking to off-crop capture by plants and bystanders).

Drop Spectra

Which measurement system to use?

Drop spectra are measured in different ways and typically models have been developed based on the drop spectra measurement system available to the modellers. For example:

- // IDEFICS and the BE CFD model: phase-doppler particle sizing (PDPA, e.g., Aerometrics)
- // SiMod: PDPA and now high-speed laser imaging (Oxford Lasers) but also laser diffraction.
- // CDM: laser diffraction (Malvern) in a constant wind speed (US drop sizing protocol).

These all differ in output and have different issues and advantages *E.g.:*

- PDPA cannot handle formulations reliably;
- Laser diffraction interpolates from a cloud of drops;
- Speed of data acquisition varies a lot.

All methods require expertise in setting up which leads to some subjectivity in the measurements. Thus, different modelled drift deposition curves can be obtained from the same nozzle at the same operating pressure. (Let's not look at formulations...)

For the future, we need some means of translating between drop size measurements – a stock library drawn from all methods?

Sampler collection efficiency

Different research institutes have used different deposition samplers.

BE: square creped filter paper, mounted on steel plates

UK: filter paper mounted on laths

DE: petri dishes

NL: filter pads in either squares or strips

Statistical analysis of the trials across gave us more questions than answers...

Country specific variability

Large-scale landscape and upwind effects on drift measurements

One outcome from the collation and statistical analysis of the >2200 drift trials in the SETAC DRAW database is that 30-40% of the variance around drift measurements is driven by the country of origin.

This is a non-intuitive result and thus makes modelling drift data a *country-specific exercise*.

[This is also the experience of SSAU (pers. comm. Clare Butler Ellis).

Possible factors are:

- // Different sampler types (already considered).
- // Large scale upwind structures (from buildings to long distance fetch) affecting the wind that passes across a drift trial.
- // Surface structure in the downwind collection area (e.g., roughness of the soil, temperature at the surface on which the samplers are laid, how the samplers are laid out)

For the future, we need a better understanding of the impact large scale and small scale meteorology applied to the scale of a field trial and to the collectors used.

France

Italy

The Netherlands

Poalnd

Consequences for the Casanova drift model

...

Any arable drift model has to be calibrated against three expectations:

1. Output needs to make sense (e.g., smaller drop spectra generate more drift).
2. The relative differences obtained in changing variables (e.g., windspeed) need to match the differences see in the field
3. The model can be tuned to properly match trial outcomes (within limits)

So far, the CDM meets the first criterium; the second needs work (and thought); and the third has been demonstrated but for very limited data sets.

Thank you!

Bye-Bye

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“MONDrift”: the Monsanto drift model

An inheritance from the takeover of Monsanto: kept very quiet!

// Mechanistic LaGrangian particle tracking model – “semi-empirical”

- // Similar in design to SSAU and PRI models (so not a new approach like CFD)
- // Built to assist Monsanto’s work with herbicide drift.
- // Already calibrated against various internal data sets (as well as AgDrift data)

The drift trial protocol ISO 22866 has been assessed and an improved template for field trials proposed.

This takes into account:

1. advances in our understanding of drift (especially meteorology)
2. the requirements of modelling (detailed information about all conditions)
3. lessons learnt testing the protocol
4. lessons derived from the analysis of the SETAC DRAW database
5. an in-depth assessment of the differences between EU MS in their trial protocols.

The protocol and all information covering the test and validation trials (IT, DE, BE, NL, FR) will be hosted alongside the SETAC DRAW database

An inheritance from the takeover of Monsanto

MonDrift

// Mechanistic LaGrangian particle tracking model – “semi-empirical”

- // Similar in design to SSAU and PRI models (so not a new approach like CFD)
- // Built to assist launch of Dicamba Tolerant soy *etc.*
- // Already calibrated against various data sets.

Spray Drift Field Study Deposition for TTI-11003

Spray Drift Field Study Deposition for ULD-12003

